

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

PHILOSOPHICAL IDEAS IN ALI KERIM'S CREATIVE WORK

Rzayeva Q.

Senior Lecturer

Agjabadi Branch of Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University, Azerbaijan

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Abstract

Ali Karim has a special role in enriching poetry with new artistic and philosophical shades in 20th century Azerbaijani literature. In his lyrics, he touched upon topics such as the meaning of human life, the problem of time and death, the contradictions of existence, and the inner freedom of man, creating a deep philosophical and psychological line in national poetry. Ali Karim's poetry combines both the traces of classical Eastern philosophy and the influences of European modernist thoughts.

In his poems, topics such as the transience of time, mortality, death and immortality have acquired a deep philosophical meaning. While defining the position of man in front of existence, the poet benefited from both the Sufi-philosophical heritage of Eastern poetry and the Western literary and philosophical tradition.

Keywords: Ali Karim, poetry, philosophical thought, death and immortality, time and mortality, inner freedom, voice of conscience, social-philosophical motifs, etc.

Ali Karim was the bearer of not only lyrical feelings, but also deep philosophical ideas in Azerbaijani poetry. His work presents the relationship between being and non-being, life and death, time and people on a broad artistic-philosophical plane.

Ali Karim's poetry opened new philosophical horizons in Azerbaijani literature by expressing man's search for inner freedom, spiritual integrity, and desire for immortality in poetic language. His work should be studied not only as a literary-artistic, but also as a deep poetic manifestation of a philosophical worldview. (2, p.17)

Four main directions come to the fore in Ali Karim's work:

1. Poetic-philosophical embodiment of the problem of time and mortality;
2. The meaning of human existence, issues of inner freedom and conscience;
3. Philosophical interpretation of the concepts of death and immortality.
4. Socio-philosophical motifs

The concept of time and mortality

Time is one of the main philosophical categories in Ali Karim's poetry. In the poet's poetry, time is not just the rhythm of nature, but a philosophical category that determines human existence. Ali Karim, along with describing the transience of human life, calls for demonstrating spiritual strength in the face of mortality. The poet presents time as both a destructive force and a factor that tests human will.

For Ali Karim, the flow of time is the main philosophical moment of human existence. In his poems, time is both a destructive force and a source of creativity. (3, p.53)

In the poem "Word of the Heart", he emphasizes the transience of human life and calls not to reconcile with mortality, but to resist it. In this regard, his poetry resonates with existential philosophical thought.

In the poem "Word of the Heart" he writes:
"The time has come, and my life is too short,

The flood has flowed, taking away the years, the days..." (1, p.35)

In these lines, time is described as a merciless force that quickly takes away human life. The metaphor of time "flood" shows that it flows without stopping and takes everything with it.

At the same time, the poet draws attention to the ability of man to leave a mark in the face of time:

"I came from the past, I am going to the future,
Time takes me, but my mark remains." (1, p.36)

Here, the concept of "mark" means the immortality of the values, deeds and words created by man. This philosophical conclusion resonates with existentialist thought: even if a person loses to time, he can win with his spiritual heritage.

Literary critic H. Mammadli writes: "In Ali Karim's poetry, time is a philosophical symbol that shows both the idea of mortality and the eternity of creativity" (Mammadli, 2010, p. 54).

The meaning of human existence, inner freedom and conscience

One of the main themes in Ali Karim's poems is the attempt of man to find the meaning of life. His heroes ask big questions about existence against the background of simple everyday events: "Who am I?", "Where did I come from?", "Where am I going?". In Ali Karim's poems, the understanding of a person's inner world and finding the purpose of his existence play an important role. (4, p.54)

Ali Karim often questions a person's position in life, the purpose of life. His heroes, based on everyday life events, turn to big philosophical questions:

"Who am I, why did I come to this world,
Am I a traveler or am I the path itself?" (1, p.47)

Here the poet expresses the questions of man before existence in poetic language. According to him, the meaning of man is not only to live, but also to create value.

The poet's approach to this subject brings him closer to both Eastern Sufi poetry and Western existentialism. In Sufism, the inner perfection of man is the

basis, and in existentialism, the inner freedom of the individual. By combining these two lines, Ali Karim shows that man confirms his existence by creating spiritual values.

The problem of death and immortality

The motif of death occupies a wide place in Ali Karim's poetry. However, death is not an end in his poems, but a new beginning, a moment that turns into immortality with the mark left by man.

According to literary critics, in Ali Karim's poetry, death is presented not only as a physical end, but also as the beginning of spiritual renewal, turning into immortality with the mark left by man.

In the poem "Stone" he writes:

"I want to leave a stone

So that I too may leave my mark in this world..." (1, p.27)

In the poem "Stone", the image of a stone is presented as an artistic symbol of a person's desire to leave a lifelong mark. The stone expresses both strength and eternity. The poet shows that a person is physically mortal, but can become immortal through his actions and the values he creates. This idea resonates with the concept known in philosophy as "the immortality of works and deeds." (5, p. 21)

This is a philosophical expression of a person's striving for immortality through his creative actions.

Literary critic S. Mammadova notes: "In Ali Karim's lyrics, death is not destruction for a person, but a new beginning, a transition to spiritual immortality" (4, p. 49).

Socio-philosophical motifs

Ali Karim's poetry is not limited to individual thoughts. In his poems, the themes of human responsibility before society, justice and human values occupy an important place. The poet sees human happiness not only on an individual level, but also in social harmony.

Karim not only touches on the problems of individual existence, but also emphasizes the responsibility of man to society. Justice, human values, and humanism are among the main ideas in his poems.

He writes:

"Not everyone can build their happiness alone,

A person is together with another, whole with the world." (1, p.64)

Here it is shown that the happiness of the individual is connected only with society, with human values. The poet's worldview is humanistic: a person should live not only for himself, but also for others.

One of the main themes of Azerbaijani poetry is the search for happiness of man. In Ali Karim's work, the motif of happiness is more often manifested in the form of longing, search, and striving for spiritual perfection. His heroes see happiness not in material goods, but in spiritual values, love, friendship, inner freedom of man, and harmony with society.

In Ali Karim's poems, happiness is often connected with the inner world of man. According to the poet, if a person remains true to his conscience, he can be happy even in a simple life. He writes:

"A sip of water, a piece of bread,

If you share it with your friend – you are happy." (1, p.47)

Here, happiness is found in the small, simple moments of everyday life. This approach directs a person away from pomp and turns him towards inner purity.

One of the main sources of happiness for the poet's lyrical heroes is love. Ali Karim presents love not only as a personal feeling, but also as a great force that perfects a person spiritually:

"In a world without love, neither the sun rises,

Nor does a person live happily." (1, p.49)

Love is the main value in his poetry that gives meaning to human life and gives happiness.

Ali Karim sees happiness not only at the individual level, but also at the social level. In his opinion, a person cannot be happy if he remains indifferent to the suffering of others:

"Not everyone can build their own happiness alone,

A person is whole with another person, whole with the world." (1, p.51)

Here, happiness is presented as a human condition. True happiness is possible only when a person is able to find happiness together with others.

In the poet's poems, happiness often appears as an unattainable ideal. This longing is connected with the poet's theme of time and mortality, which we mentioned above. Although he desires happiness, he constantly reminds us of the transience of the world:

"One day will come, the world is mortal,

Happiness also passes like a dream." (1, p.52)

These verses reveal the philosophical side of the longing for happiness: a person seeks happiness, but the ruthlessness of time makes this feeling temporary.

Ali Karim's poetry constitutes the most important stage of philosophical lyricism in Azerbaijani literature. In his poems, topics such as the transience of time, the meaning of life, death and immortality, and the position of man before society carry a deep philosophical meaning.

The philosophical aspect of Ali Karim's lyrics should be evaluated as a valuable example not only of Azerbaijani literature, but also of universal poetry. The idea of humanism is the leading line in his work: a person should own his spiritual values and live a meaningful life not only for himself, but also for society.

Ali Karim's poetry is not built only on individual thoughts. His poems also raise philosophical questions about society, justice, and the fate of mankind. The poet emphasizes that a person will not be satisfied with only his individual happiness, and the importance of commitment to human values. These ideas form the basis of a humanistic worldview in his lyrics. (6, p.85)

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